

ASSESSING THE POTENTIAL OF CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS CONTENT IN EUROPEAN STEEL SLAG

Futu

Future availability
of secondary
raw materials

RaM

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Objectives

- FutuRaM project : estimate the contribution to the EU demand in terms of Critical Raw Materials from different waste streams
- The work present here → assess the potential future availability of Critical Raw Materials in European **steel slags**
- CRM Act adopted in 2024. 25% of EU CRM demand should come from recycling
- **Workplan**
 - Compile data on steel slag CRM content (literature review)
 - Assess future slag production following 3 scenarios
 - Assess potential CRM recovery

Steel slags

- Previous European or national projects investigated & developed processes for metal recovery
- Current situation: valorisation in cement/road construction
- Historical heaps. Polluted sites
 - depollution/rehabilitation,
 - land recovery and
 - material valorisation

Communication

Innovative Process for Strategic Metal Recovery from Electric Arc Furnace Slag by Alkaline Leaching

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Open Access Article

Multi-Analytical Characterization of Slags to Determine the Chromium Concentration for a Possible Re-Extraction

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Ex-ante LCA of emerging carbon steel slag treatment technologies: Fast forwarding lab observations to industrial-scale production

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Steel slag composition

- Literature review of 25 articles giving chemical composition of steel slags
- Different types of slags
 - BF
 - BOF
 - EAF (carbon steel, stainless, unknown)
 - Ladle
 - Historical heaps (Hypass & Regeneratis projects)

Element	BOF slag	EAF slag	Ladle slag	Mining ore grade ¹
V	0.077 to 2.7 (1.4)	0.031 to 0.09 (0.09)	0.028 to 0.28 (0.15)	0.12
Cr	0.05 to 3.4 (0.9)	0.19 to 3.3 (1.2)	0.007 to 0.33 (0.15)	27
Ti	0.4 to 1.4 (0.87)	0.24 to 1.3 (0.6)	0.08 to 0.53 (0.23)	1.59

Scenarios storytelling

- Business as usual (BAU).
 - EAF/BOF steel production stable in Europe (8 last years)
 - Current slags valorisation options (cement, road aggregate, Fe recovery)
- Recovery (REC).
 - Steel production stable like BAU
 - Progressively, **substitution of BOF** capacity in Europe by EAF until 60% of EAF in 2040
 - Less landfill.
 - A part of slags are diverted to Critical Raw Materials recovery
 - Construction of 2 vanadium recovery plants like Novana project
- Circular (CIR)
 - Same that REC but more circular society, less scrap to recycle
 - **Reduction of steel production** in Europe without a big disruption

Steel production to
slag production

Ratios based on
Piemonti et al (2022)
ratios

BAU scenario

Slag production per year in Europe in BAU scenario

REC & CIR scenario

Slag production per year in Europe in REC scenario

Slag production per year in Europe in CIR scenario

Recovery model

Recovery ratios

Table 3. Extraction of Metal, Different Techniques, Process Conditions, and Amount of Metal Recovery from Different Types of Slag of the Steel Industry

slag type	metal recovered	recovery (%)	technique applied
BOF slag	iron	93.20	magnetic separation
EAF slag	iron	90	drum magnetic separation
BOF slag	iron	95	reduction
LD-slag	iron	66	magnetic separation (MS)
steel slag	chromium	83	alkali roasting
BOF slag	chromium	84	bioleaching
steel slag	vanadium	87.9	roasting followed by leaching
steel slag	vanadium	28.7	precipitation
EAF slag	manganese	100	acid leaching
BOF slag	manganese	80	hydrothermal leaching
steel slag	manganese, chromium	85.99, 95.24	argon oxygen decarburization (AOD) techn

At laboratory
scale good
metal
recovery
ratios

Results - vanadium

- V content in BOF slag flow for 3 scenarios
- No recovery from historical heaps
- Context: Vanadium global primary production 91 kt/y (SCRREEN factsheet)

Limits

- Heterogeneities in slag composition. In reality, only rich CRM slags would go to CRM recovery
- Uncertainties on steelmaking sector in EU. Place of hydrogen, realism of big EAF conversion, geopolitics
- Euroslag stat data presents data gaps
- Bad knowledge of EU historical steel slag heaps. Historical heaps are not considered in scenario annual flows when industrial projects target this resource
- OPEX/CAPEX considerations of metal recovery in scenarios

Conclusions

- **Significant Waste Volume** : Iron/Steel slag represents a large volume of annual waste in Europe (around 35 Mt/year), requiring bulk material solutions (aggregates, cement, etc.).
- **Hydrometallurgy Processes Development** : Hydrometallurgy processes for recovering critical raw materials (V, Ti, Cr...) have been developed recently, but industrial upscaling remains challenging.
- **Low Percentage of Critical Materials** : Despite their strategic and economic importance, critical raw materials represent a low percentage (~1 to 2%) of the slag, posing a major management issue for the remaining waste flow.
- However, **potentially total V content** in steel slags can represent compared to primary production. But less BOF, less V recoverable in flows!
- **Conditions for Successful Recovery Projects** : Initiatives like Novana vanadium recovery project in Finland show that CRM recovery projects can emerge if certain conditions are met:
 - high CRM content in the initial slag,
 - constant slag flow + historical heap,
 - mature recovery technology,
 - and a solution for managing the remaining flow

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Thank you!

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